

ILMIY-TEXNIKA JURNALI

 Farg'ona
Politexnika
Instituti

Scientific - technical journal

Научно-технический журнал
Ферганского
политехнического
института

2022. СПЕЦ. ВЫПУСК № 10

ISSN 2181-7200

ЎЗБЕКИСТОН РЕСПУБЛИКАСИ ОЛИЙ ВА ЎРТА
МАХСУС ТАЪЛИМ ВАЗИРЛИГИ

ФАРҒОНА ПОЛИТЕХНИКА ИНСТИТУТИ

И Л М И Й – Т Е Х Н И К А Ж У Р Н А Л И

2022. СПЕЦ. ВЫПУСК № 10

*НАУЧНО–ТЕХНИЧЕСКИЙ
ЖУРНАЛ ФерПИ*

*SCIENTIFIC – TECHNICAL
JOURNAL of FerPI*

ФАРҒОНА – 2022

ФарПИ ИЛМИЙ-ТЕХНИКА ЖУРНАЛИ ТАХРИРИЯТИ

1997 йилдан буён нашр этилади.
Йилга 6 марта чоп қилинади.

ЎзР Олий аттестация комиссияси
Раёсатининг 2013 йил 30 декабрдаги
№201/3 қарори билан журнал ОАК нинг
илмий нашрлари рўйхатига киритилган

Бош муҳаррир

Ў.Р. САЛОМОВ

Тахрир хайъати:

Физика-математика фанлари:

1. Вайткус Ю.Ю., академик, ф.-м.ф.д., проф. –Вильнюс, Литва ДУ
2. Тарасенко С.А., ф.-м.ф.д., проф. –С-Пб. ФТИ, РФА
3. Мўминов Р.А., академик, ф.-м.ф.д., проф. – Ўз ФА ФТИ
4. Сиддиков Б.М., Prof. of Mathem. – Ferris State University, USA
5. Нуриддинов И., ф.-м.ф.д., проф. – Ўз ФА ЯФИ
6. Юлдашев Н.Х., ф.-м.ф.д., проф. – Фар ПИ

Механика:

1. Алиматов Б.А., т.ф.д., проф. – Белгород ДТУ, Россия
2. Сиваченко Л.А., академик, д.т.н., проф. – Бел.-Рос. Университет, Беларусия
3. Бойбобоев Н., т.ф.д., проф. – Нам МКИ
4. Мамаджанов А.М. т.ф.д., проф. – Тош ДТУ
5. Тожиев Р.Ж., т.ф.д., проф. – Фар ПИ
6. Тўхтақўзиёв А., т.ф.д., проф. – Ўз ФА МЭИ

Қурилиш:

1. Аббасов Ё.С., т.ф.д. – Фар ПИ
2. Ақромов Х.А., т.ф.д., проф. – Тош АҚИ
3. Одилхажаяев А.Э., т.ф.д., проф. – Тош ТИТМИ
4. Раззаков С.Ж., т.ф.д., проф. – НамМКИ
5. Шинкова Н.Б. т.ф.д. проф. – Москва Арх. Инст., Россия

Энергетика, электротехника, электрон қурилмалар ва ахборот технологиялар

1. Арипов Н.М., т.ф.д., проф. – Тошкент ТИТМИ
2. Хайриддинов Б.Э., т.ф.д., проф. – Қарши ДУ
3. Касымамунова А.М., т.ф.д., проф. – Фар ПИ
4. Расулов А.М., т.ф.д. – ТАТУ ФФ
5. Эргашев С.Ф., т.ф.д. – Фар ПИ

Кимёвий технология ва экология

1. Абдурахимов С.А., т.ф.д. проф. – Тош ДТУ
2. Ибрагимов А.А., к.ф.д., проф. – Фар ДУ
3. Ибрагимов О.О., к.х.ф.д. – Фар ПИ
4. Омонов Т.С., ф.-м.ф.д., проф. –Альберта Университети, Эдмонтон, Канада.
5. Хамдамова Ш.Ш., т.ф.д. – Фар ПИ
6. Хамроқулов З.А., т.ф.д. – Фар ПИ

Ижтимоий-иқтисодий фанлар

1. Ертаев К.Е., и.ф.д., проф. – Тараз ДУ, Қозғистон
2. Иқромов М.А., и.ф.д., проф. – Тош ИУ
3. Искандарова Ш.М., фил.ф.д., проф. – Фар ДУ
4. Исманов И.Н., и.ф.д., проф. – Фар ПИ
5. Кудбиев Д., и.ф.д., проф. – Фар ПИ

НАУЧНО-ТЕХНИЧЕСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ ФерПИ

Издаётся с 1997 года.
Выходит 6 раз в год.

Постановлением Президиума Высшей
аттестационной комиссии РУз №201/3
от 30 декабря 2013 г. журнал включен в
список научных изданий ВАК.

Главный редактор

Ў.Р. САЛОМОВ

Редакционная коллегия:

Ё.С. Аббасов, С.А. Абдурахимов, Б.А. Алиматов, Х.А. Ақромов, Н.М. Арипов, Н. Бойбобоев, Ю.Ю. Вайткус, К.Е. Ертаев, А.А. Ибрагимов, О.О. Ибрагимов, М.А. Иқромов, Ш.М. Искандарова, И.Н. Исманов, А.М. Касымамунова, Д. Кудбиев, А.М. Мамаджанов, Р.А. Муминов, И. Нуриддинов, А.Э. Одилхажаяев, Т.С. Омонов, А.М. Расулов, С.Ж. Раззаков, З.М. Сатторов, Б. Сиддиков, Л.А. Сиваченко, С.А. Тарасенко, Р.Ж. Тожиев, А.А. Тўхтақўзиёв, Б.Э. Хайриддинов, Ш.Ш. Хамдамова, З.А. Хамроқулов, Н.Б. Шинкова, С.Ф. Эргашев, Н.Х. Юлдашев (ответственный редактор)

SCIENTIFIC – TECHNICAL JOURNAL of FerPI

It has been published since 1997.
It is printed 6 times a year.

The decision of Presidium of the Supreme
Attestation Committee of the RUz №201/3
from December, 30th, 2013 Journal is included
in the list of scientific editions of the SAC.

Editor-in-chief

О' .R. SALOMOV

Editorial board members:

Yo.S. Abbasov, S.A. Abdurahimov, B.A. Alimatov, X.A. Akromov, N.M. Aripov, N. Boyboboiev, Yu.Yu. Vitkus, K.E. Ertaev, A.A. Ibragimov, O.O. Ibragimov, M.A. Ikramov, Sh.M. Iskandarova, I.N. Ismanov, A.M. Kasimahunova, D. Kudbiev, A.M. Mamadjanov, R.A. Muminov, I. Nuritdinov, A.O. Odilxajayev, T.S. Omonov, A.M. Rasulov, S.J. Razzakov, Z.M. Sattorov, B. Siddikov, L.A. Sivachenko, S.A. Tarasenko, R.J. Tojiev, A.A. Tuxtakuziev, B.E. Hayriddinov, Sh.Sh. Xamdamova, Z.A. Xamroqulov, N.B. Shinkova, S.F. Ergashev, N.Kh.Yuldashev (Executive Editor)

МУНДАРИЖА

МЕХАНИКА

Тожиев Р.Ж., Сулаймонов А.М. Чангли газларни ҳўл усулда тозаловчи тарелкали скруббернинг макбул параметрларини математик моделлаштириш	9
Tojiev R.J., Alizafarov B.M. Konveyer lentalarining cho'zilish, barabanlardagi egilish va tortish kuchini uzatilishidan charchab eskirishini eksperimental tadqiqoti	15
Срождинов Ж.Р., Мухторов Ш.С. Детал юзаларининг қаттиқлигини цементация усули билан ошириш ..	25

ҚУРИЛИШ

Акрамов Х.А., Умаров Ш.А. Шиша толали композит арматурали эгилувчи бетон тўсинларни синаш	31
Kimsanov Z.O. Sanoat binolarini loyihalashda arxitektura yechimlar	37
Abdullaev I.N., Muxamedzyanov A.R. Tuz agressiyasi oshidagi yassi sement-beton turkishlari	43
Ismoilov M.M. Quyosh issiq suv ta'minoti tizimlarida tekis quyosh kollektorlarining ish parametrlarini optimallashtirish	48

ЭНЕРГЕТИКА, ЭЛЕКТРОТЕХНИКА, ЭЛЕКТРОН ҚУРИЛМАЛАР ВА АХБОРОТ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАР

Quchqarov A.A., Abduraimov A.A., Obidjonov Z.O., Aliev A.A. Parabolik silindrsimon oynani kontsentratsiyalash tizimlari uchun quyoshdan keladigan nurlanish oqimining zichligini hisoblashning analitik yondashuvlari	53
Abdumanonov A.A. Zamonaviy mobil qurilmalarning talabalar o'zlashtirishiga ta'siri	57
Quchqarov A.A., Xoshimov D.U., Raxmatshoev I.N., Jumaboev A. Energiyani saqlash tizimlarini to'liq sharxi: texnologiyalarni baholash va tarmoq miqyosidagi qo'llanilishi	64
Salomov O'R., Payzullaxanov M.S., Quchqarov A.A., Xolmatov A.A. "FIZIKA-QUYOSH" IIBda sintez qilingan Ba-Fe-O, Bi-Fe-O ferritlarining kristall tuzilishi va magnit xossalari	71

КИМЁВИЙ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ ВА ЭКОЛОГИЯ

Эргашев Д.А., Хамдамова Ш.Ш, Отақўзиев Т.Т. Ca(NO ₃) ₂ -Mg(NO ₃) ₂ -H ₂ O системадаги компонентларнинг эрувчанлигини ўрганиш	77
Маруфжонов М.А. Қуритилган мевалар компотининг физик-кимёвий кўрсаткичларини аниқлаш усуллари ўрганиш	81
Akrmov A.A. Ichimlik suvi tozalashda loyqalanish jarayonlarini tindirgichlariga ta'sirini baholash	86

ИЖТИМОЙ-ИҚТИСОДИЙ ФАНЛАР

Shakirova Yu.S., Sotvoldiyeva M.G. To'qimachilik va paxta sanoati tarmoqlariga innovatsion texnologiyalarni rivojlantirish masalalari	92
Мадаминов Ж.З. Техника олий таълим муассасалари талабаларида муҳандислик ва компютер графикаси бўйича амалий-ижодий кўникмалар шакллантириш ва ривожлантириш методларини такомиллаштириш (Лойиҳалаш фаолияти мисолида)	96
Kodirova D.T. Umumiy kimyoviy texnologiya fanidan pedagogik texnologiyalarni qo'llash	101
Gorovik A.A., Mamadaliyeva L.K., Zulunov R.M. Maqsadga erishishni baholash usuli asosida xodimlarni rag'batlantirish	106

ҚИСҚА ХАБАРЛАР

Sultanov N.A. Kumush qo'shilgan kremniyning fotoluminesansi	112
Nasirov M.X. O'lchamli kvantlashgan yarim o'tkazgichli tizimlar	114
Abdurazakov A., Mirzamahmudova N., Mahmudova N. Oliy matematika fanini o'qitishda informatsion texnologiyalar(MathCad, Maple)dan foydalanish	118
Sodiqova G.A. $y''(t) = y'(1/t)$ tenglamani J.Wiener usulida yechish	124
Tilavaldiyev B.T. Mexanik uzatmalarni hisoblashda ishlatiladigan moylash materiallarini (moylar) yopishqoqligini tanlash va aniqlash	126
Баҳадиров Г.А., Умаров Б.Т., Турсуналиев И.Э., Тождидинов С.Х. Картошка туганакларини вибрацион саралаш машинаси ишчи юзасидаги ҳаракатининг математик моделини ишлаб чиқиш	129
Do'smatov A.D., Mamajonov B.A. Xarorat tasirida bo'lgan metall va shishaplastik qatlamlardan iborat silindrsimon qobiqlarni nometall qatlamini torayish deformatsiyasi masalasi	133
Тураев Т.Т., Мадаминов Б.М. Машина деталларини яшовчанлигини оширишда ишлов беришнинг макбул усулини танлаш	136
Madaminov B.M., Nishonova G.G. Kimyo sanoati mashina va jihozlarini agressiv muhitdan himoya qilish muammolari	140
Сулаймонов О.Н., Эргашева Ф. Аррали жинларнинг унумдорлигини ошириш йўллари	143
Xomidov V.O., Turdimatova M.A., Xalilova D.J. Tola qomatdagi ayollar sport kiyimi toplami uchun gazlama tanlash	146
Kimsanov B.I., Nazirov A.S. Qurilishda kompozit armaturalarning qo'llanish sohalari va tasnifi	148
Davlyatov Sh.M., Nazirov A.S. Kompozit materiallardan tashqi armaturalashning konstruktiv xususiyatlari	152

Abobakirova Z.A., Bobofozilov O.M., Karroziyaga chidamli beton xususiyatlarini oshirish uchun polimer qo‘shimcha	156
Goncharova N.I., Muxamedzyanov A.R., Saidumarova U. Kvartirali binolar va ko‘p funktsiyali turar-joy majmualari	159
Nabiyev M., Musajonov M., A‘zamjonov A. Shahar ko‘chalarini obodonlashtirish, manzarali o‘simliklar ekish usullari va sxemalari	163
Абдуразақов А.М., Мусажонов М.А. Паст ҳароратли истиш тизимларидаги шамоллатиш радиаторларнинг иссиқлик узатиш қобилиятларини аниқлаш йўллари ва уларнинг таҳлили	165
Mamatov O.M. Quyosh batareyalarini issiqlik va namlik sharoitlarida tadqiq qilish uchun radiomodulli arduino simsiz harorat monitori ishlab chiqish	168
Fozilov I.R. Avtomatlashtirilgan tizimlarda ma‘lumotlar bazasi xavfsizligiga tahdid	170
Karimov N.U. Kuch transformatorlari ishlab samaradorligiga izalatsiyalovchi moyning ta‘siri va moyni qayta ishlash	173
Yusupov D.T., Muhammadjonov M.Sh., Abduraximov D.R. Moyli kuch transformatorlaridagi yuqori haroratning ishlash ishonchligiga ta‘siri	175
Quchqarov A.A., Abduraimov A.A., Obidjonov Z.O., Aliyev A.A., Yo‘ldasheva N.R. Quyosh kollektorlarining sirtida hosil bo‘luvchi haroratni masofadan o‘lchash	179
Usmonov Sh.Yu. Energetik resurslarni tejovchi va ekologik mukammal texnologiyalar	182
Madaminov M.R., Xosilov D.D., Yo‘ldashev X.T. Mobil tarmoqlarining baza stansiyalarida zaxira energiya ta‘minot manbaalarining energetik samaradorligini oshirish	185
Rasakhodjaev B.S., Quchqarov A.A., Boboeva M.O., Mashrapova I.R., Mamasadiqova Z.Yu. Issikxonadagi quyosh energiyasini akkumuliyasiya jarayonini tadqiq qilish	188
Haydarov B.Z., Hakimov M.F., Dadajonova M.K. Gaz chiqarish xujayrasi asosida ob'ektlarni infraqizil suratga olish	191
Холиддинов И.Х. Радиал электр таъминоти схемаси истеъмолчилари ўртасида компенсация қурилмаларнинг оптимал қувват тақсими	195
Eraliyev X.A., Ibrohimov I.Z. Nossimetrik yuklangan transformatorlardagi qo‘shimcha yo‘qotishlarni hisoblash ...	199
Meliboyev I.A. Chiqindi gazlarni zararsizlantirish va tozalash usullari	202
Alimova Z.X., Ishmadiyov A.A. O‘zbekiston sharoitida ishlatiladigan dizelli dvigatel moylarini ekspluatatsion xossalarini qo‘shilmalar yordamida yaxshilash	205
Карабасва М.И. Ўсимлик чиқиндилари асосида углеродли адсорбентлар олиш ва уларнинг адсорбцион хоссаларини ўрганиш	208
Asqarov X.X. Mosh (rhaseolis aires piper)ning navro‘z navi o‘sishi, rivojlanishini tahliliy o‘rganish	211
Mirsalimova S.R., Jakbarov D.V. Benzimidazol hosilalarining sintezi va xossalarini o‘rganish	214
Собиров А.О. Фарғона вилоятининг шўрланган тупроқлари ва ундан фойдаланиш	216
Eminov Sh.O. Paxtani qayta ishlash mashinalari ishchi organlarining kompozitsion polimer qoplamalarini xossalarini o‘rganish	220
Arziyev S.S. Muhandislik kompyuter grafikasi fanini o‘qitishda gologrammalardan foydalanish samaradorligi	222
Олтмишева Н.Г., Тожибоев У.У. Ўзбекистонда демократик янгилаш ва модернизация жараёнлари	224
Maxmudov S.Y. Kundalik faoliyat sharoitlarida ionlashtiruvchi nurlanishlardan muhofazalanish	227
Abdullayeva M.A., Mirzaakbarov Q.Z. Texnika oliy o‘quv yurtlarida yarimo‘tkazgichli rele himoyasi qurilmalarini o‘qitishning yangi interaktiv usullarini yaratish	229
Nishonova M.M. Intellektual tizimlarni ta‘lim jarayonida qo‘llash muammolari va yechimlari	233
Fozilov H.R. Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida milliy statistika tizimidagi ayrim muammolar va ularni bartaraf etish yo‘llari	235
Исомитдинова Г.К. Рақамли иқтисодиёт шaroitida инвестиция жозибadorлигини баҳолашнинг хорижий давлат тажрибаси	238
Abidova M.A. Yetuk mutahassis muhandis-texnologlarni yetishtirishda yangi pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalanish	240
Хайдаров А.А. Органик кимё фанидан “Озиқ - овқат технология”си йўналиши талабаларини ўқитишнинг инновацион усуллари	243
Mirzaeva G.S., Gafurovm M. Xavfli yuklarni tashish bilan shug'ullanadigan haydovchilarning ish sharoitlarini yaxshilash chorolari	246
Ergashov U.O. Ma‘naviy ishlarni tashkil etishning maqsad va vazifalari	249
Axunova M.X. To‘qimachilik sanoatini rivojlantirishning dolzarb masalalari	251
Ўринбоева М.С. Ёшлар ва экологик ахлоқ нормалари	253
Муаллифлар диққатига !	257

СОДЕРЖАНИЕ

МЕХАНИКА

Тожиев Р.Ж., Сулаймонов А.М. Математическое моделирование допустимых параметров очистки тарельчатого скруббера от запыленных газов мокрым способом	9
Тожиев Р.Ж., Ализафаров Б.М. Экспериментальное исследование усталостного износа лент при растяжении, изгибе на барабанах и передаче тягового усилия	15
Срождинов Ж.Р., Мухторов Ш.С. Повышение твердости поверхностей деталей методом цементации	25

СТРОИТЕЛЬСТВО

Акрамов Х.А., Умаров Ш.А. Испытания изгибаемых бетонных балок со стекловолокнистой композитной арматурой	31
Кимсанов З.О. Архитектурные решения при проектировании промышленных зданий	37
Абдуллаев И.Н., Мухамедзянов А.Р. Плоские цементобетонные конструкции в условиях солевой агрессии	43
Исмоилов М.М. Оптимизация режимных параметров плоских солнечных коллекторов в системах солнечного горячего водоснабжения	48

ЭНЕРГЕТИКА, ЭЛЕКТРОТЕХНИКА, ЭЛЕКТРОННЫЕ ПРИБОРЫ И ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ

Кучкаров А.А., Абдураимов А.А., Обиджонов З.О., Алиев А.А. Аналитические подходы расчета распределения плотности лучистого потока от солнца для параболоцилиндрических зеркально - концентрирующих систем	53
Абдуманов А.А. Влияние современных мобильных устройств на успеваемость студентов	57
Кучкаров А.А., Хошимов Д.У., Рахматшоев И.Н., Джумабоев А. Всесторонний обзор систем накопления энергии: оценка технологий и применение в масштабах сети	64
Саломов У.Р., Пайзуллаханов М.С., Кучкаров А.А., Холматов А.А. Кристаллическая структура и магнитные свойства ферритов Ва-Fe-O, Ви-Fe-O, синтезированных в НПО «ФИЗИКА-СОЛНЦЕ»	71

ХИМИЧЕСКАЯ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ И ЭКОЛОГИЯ

Эргашев Д.А., Хамдамова Ш.Ш., Отакузиев Т.Т. Растворимость компонентов в системе $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2\text{-Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2\text{-H}_2\text{O}$	77
Маруфжонов М.А. Изучение методов определения физико-химических показателей компота из сухофруктов	81
Акрмов А.А. Оценка влияния процессов помутнения на умягчители при очистке питьевой воды	86

СОЦИАЛЬНО - ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИЕ НАУКИ

Шакирова Ю.С., Сотволдиева М.Г. Вопросы разработки инновационных технологий для сетей текстильной и хлопкопромышленной промышленности	92
Мадаминов Ж.З. Совершенствование методов формирования и развития практических и творческих навыков инженерной и компьютерной графики у студентов технических вузов (на примере проектной деятельности)	96
Кодирова Д.Т. Применение педагогических технологий в общей химической технологии	101
Горовик А.А., Мамадалиева Л.К., Зулунув Р.М. Стимулирование сотрудников на основе метода оценки достижения цели	106

КРАТКИЕ СООБЩЕНИЯ

Султанов Н.А. Фотолуминесценция кремния легированного серебром	112
Насиров М.Х. Размерные квантованные полупроводниковые системы	114
Абдуразаков А., Мирзамахмудова Н., Махмудова Н. Использование информационных технологий (MathCad, Maple) в обучении высшей математике	118
Содиқова Г.А. $y''(t) = y'(1/t)$ решение уравнения методом Дж. Винера	124
Тилавалдиев Б.Т. Выбор вязкости и определение используемых смазочных материалов (масла) при расчете механических передач	126
Бахадиров Г.А., Умаров Б.Т., Турсуналиев И.Э., Тожиддинов С.Х. Разработка математической модели движения клубней картофеля по рабочей поверхности вибрационной сортировочной машины	129
Дусматов А.Д., Мамажонов Б.А. Температурная задача металло-стеклопластиковых оболочек с учётом усадки неметаллического слоя	133
Тураев Т.Т., Мадаминов Б.М. Повышение долговечности деталей машин путем выбора оптимального метода обработки	136
Мадаминов Б.М., Нишонова Г.Г. Проблемы защиты машин и оборудования химической промышленности от агрессивных сред	140
Сулаймонов О.Н., Эргашева Ф. Пути повышения производительности пыльных джинов	143
Хомидов В.О., Турдиматова М.А., Халилова Д.Ж. Выбираем ткань для женского спортивного комплекта для полных женщин	146
Кимсанов Б.И., Назиров А.С. Область применения и классификация композитной арматуры в строительстве	148
Давлятов Ш.М., Назиров А.С. Конструктивные особенности выполнения внешнего армирования из композиционных материалов	152

СОДЕРЖАНИЕ

Абобакирова З.А., Бобофозилов О.М., Полимерная добавка для улучшения свойств коррозионостойкого бетона	156
Гончарова Н.И., Мухамедзянов А.Р., Саидумарова У. Доходные дома и многофункциональные жилые комплексы	159
Набиев М., Мусаджонов М., Азамджонов А. Озеленение городских улиц, способы и схемы посадки декоративных растений	163
Абдуразаков А.М., Мусажонов М.А. Способы определения теплопроводности вентиляционных радиаторов в низкотемпературных системах и их анализ	165
Маматов О.М. Разработка беспроводного температурного монитора arduino с радио модулем для исследования солнечных элементов в условиях жары и влажности	168
Фозилов И.Р. Угроза безопасности баз данных в автоматизированных системах	170
Каримов Н.У. Влияние изоляционного масла и переработки масла на работу силового трансформатора	173
Юсупов Д.Т., Мухаммаджонов М.Ш., Абдурахимов Д.Р. Влияние высокой температуры на надежность работы силовых масляных трансформаторов	175
Кучкаров А.А., Абдураимов А.А., Обиджонов З.О., Алиев А.А., Йулдашева Н.Р. Дистанционное измерение температуры, генерируемой на поверхности солнечных коллекторов	179
Усмонов Ш.Ю. Энергосберегающие и экологически совершенные технологии	182
Мадаминов М.Р., Хосилов Д.Д., Йулдашев Х.Т. Повышение энергоэффективности резервных источников энергоснабжения в базовых станциях сети мобильная связь	185
Расаходжаев Б.С., Кучкаров А.А., Бобоева М.О., Машрапова И.Р. Мамасадикова З.Ю. Исследование процесса аккумуляции солнечной энергии в теплицах	188
Хайдаров Б.З., Хакимов М.Ф., Дадажонов М.К. Инфракрасное фотографирование объектов на основе газоразрядной ячейки	191
Холиддинов И.Х. Оптимальное распределение мощности компенсирующих устройств между потребителями радиальной схемы электроснабжения	195
Эралиев Х.А., Иброхимов И.З. Расчет дополнительных потерь в трансформаторах с несимметричной нагрузкой	199
Мелибоев И.А. Методы обезвреживания и очистки отходящих газов	202
Алимова З.Х., Исмадиёров А.А. Улучшение эксплуатационных свойств дизельных масел, применяемых в условиях Узбекистана	205
Карабаева М.И. Получение углеродных адсорбентов на основе растительных отходов и изучение их адсорбционных свойств	208
Аскарлов Х.Х. Аналитическое исследование роста и развития браги сорта Новруз (rhaseol is aireis piper)	211
Мирсалимова С.Р., Жакбаров Д.В. Исследование синтеза и свойства производных бензимидазол	214
Собиров А.О. Засоленные почвы ферганской области и их использование	216
Эминов Ш.О. Изучение свойств композиционных полимерных покрытий рабочих органов хлопкоперерабатывающих машин	220
Арзиев С.С. Эффективность использования голограмм в преподавании дисциплины инженерная компьютерная графика	222
Олтмишева Н.Г., Тожибоев У.У. Процессы демократического обновления и модернизации в Узбекистане	224
Махмудов С.Ю. Защита от ионизирующего излучения в повседневной деятельности	227
Абдуллаева М.А. Мирзаакбаров К.З. Создание новых интерактивных методик обучения устройств полупроводниковой релейной защиты в технических ВУЗах	229
Нишонов М.М. Проблемы и решения использования интеллектуальных систем в образовательном процессе	233
Фозилов Х.Р. Некоторые проблемы в системе национальной статистики в условиях цифровой экономики и пути их решения	235
Исомитдинова Г.К. Зарубежный государственный опыт оценки инвестиционной привлекательности в условиях цифровой экономики	238
Абидова М.А. Использование новых педагогических технологий в подготовке специалистов инженеров-технологов	240
Хайдаров А.А. Инновационные методы обучения студентов отделения «Технология пищевых продуктов» органической химии	243
Мирзаева Г.С., Гафуров М. Мероприятия по улучшению условий труда водителей занятых перевозкой опасных грузов	246
Эргашов У.О. Цели и задачи организации духовного дела	249
Ахунова М.Х. Актуальные вопросы развития текстильной промышленности	251
Уринбоева М.С. Молодежь и нормы экологической этики	253
К сведению авторов !	258

CONTENTS

MECHANICS

Tojiyev R.J., Sulaymonov A.M. Mathematical modeling of the acceptable parameters of the plate scrubber cleaning dusty gases in the wet method	9
Tojiyev R.J., Alizafarov B.M. Experimental investigation of fatigue wear of belts under stretching, bending on drums and transmission of driving force	15
Srojidinov J.R., Mukhtorov Sh.S. Increasing the hardness of detail surfaces by the cementation method	25

BUILDING

Akramov Kh.A., Umarov Sh.A. Testing of a reinforced concrete beam with fiberglass composite reinforcement	31
Kimsanov Z.O. Architectural solutions in designing industrial buildings	37
Abdullaev I.N., Muxamedzyanov A.R. Flat cement concrete structures under salt aggression	43
Ismoilov M.M. Optimization of operating parameters of flat solar collectors in solar hot water supply systems	48

ENERGETICS, THE ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING, ELECTRONIC DEVICES AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES

Kuchkarov A.A., Abduraimov A.A., Obidjonov Z.O., Aliev A.A. Analytical Approaches for Calculating the density distribution of radiant flux from the sun for parabolic cylindrical mirror-concentrating systems	53
Abdumananov A.A. The influence of modern mobile devices on the performance of students	57
Kuchkarov A.A., Khoshimov D.U., Rakhmatshoev I.N., Jumaboev A. A comprehensive review of energy storage systems: technologies appraisal and grid scale applications	64
Salomov U.R., Paizullakhanov M.S., Kuchkarov A.A., Xolmatov A.A. Crystal structure and magnetic properties ferrites Ba-Fe-O, Bi-Fe-O, synthesized in NGO "PHYSICS-SUN"	71

CHEMICAL TECHNOLOGY AND ECOLOGY

Ergashev D.A., Xamdanova Sh.Sh., Otaq'ziyev T.T. The study of the solubility of component in system $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2\text{-Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2\text{-H}_2\text{O}$	77
Маруфжонов М.А. Studying the methods of determining the physical and chemical indicators of dried fruit compote	81
Akrmov A.A. Evaluation of the influence of turbidity processes on drinking water treatment plants	86

SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC SCIENCES

Shakirova Yu.S., Sotvoldiyeva M.G'. Directions for the development of the fruit and vegetable market of Uzbekistan and its export potential	92
Madaminov J.Z. Improving methods of formation and development of practical and creative skills in engineering and computer graphics among students of technical higher education institutions (as an example of design activity)	96
Kodirova D.T. Application of pedagogical technologies in general Chemical Technology	101
Gorovik A.A., Mamadalieva L.K., Zulunov R.M. Incentivization of employees based on the method of assessing the achievement of the goal	106

SHORT MESSAGES

Sultanov N.A. Photoluminescence of silver-doped silicon	112
Nasirov M.X. Dimensional quantized semiconductor systems	114
Abdurazakov A., Mirzamahmudova N., Mahmudova N. The use of information technology (MathCad, Maple) in teaching higher mathematics	118
Sodikova G.A. $y''(x) = y'(1/x)$ solving the equation by the method of J. Wiener	124
Tilavaldiyev B.T. The choice of viscosity and the determination of the lubricants (oils) used in the calculation of mechanical transmissions	126
Bakhadirov G.A., Umarov B.T., Tursunaliyev I.E., Tojiddinov S.Kh. Development of a mathematical model of the movement of potato tubers on the working surface of a vibration sorting machine	129
Dosmatov A.D., Mamajonov B.A. The problem of deformation of the mirror layer of cylindrical shells consisting of metal and glass-plastic layers under the influence of temperature	133
Turaev T.T., Madaminov B.M. Increasing the durability of machine parts by selecting the optimal method of processing	136
Madaminov B.M., Nishonova G.G. Problems of protection of machines and equipment of the chemical industry from aggressive environment	140
Sulaymonov O.N., Ergasheva F. Ways to improve the performance of saw gins	143
Khomidov V.O., Turdimatova M.A., Khalilova D.J. Choosing a fabric for a women's sports kit for overweight women	146
Kimsanov B.I., Nazirov A.S. Application and classification of composite reinforcement in construction	148
Davlyatov Sh.M., Nazirov A.S. Construction features of performing external reinforcement from composite materials	152

CONTENTS

Abobakirova Z.A., Bobofozilov O.M., Polymer admixture for improving the properties of corrosion-resistant concrete	156
Goncharova N.I., Muxamedzyanov A.R., Saidumarova U. Apartment buildings and multifunctional residential complexes	159
Nabiyev M., Musajonov M., Azamjonov A. Landscaping of city streets, methods and schemes of planting ornamental plants	163
Abdurazakov A.M. Musajonov M.A. Methods for determining thermal conductivity of ventilation radiators in low-temperature systems and their analysis	165
Mamatov O.M. Development of an arduino wireless temperature monitor with a radio module for researching solar cells under heat and humidity conditions	168
Fozilov I.R. Database security threat in automated systems	170
Karimov N.U. Effect of insulating oil and oil recycling on power transformer performance	173
Yusupov D.T., Muhammadjonov M.Sh., Abduraximov D.R. Effect of high temperature on reliability of operation of oil power transformers	175
Kuchkarov A.A., Abduraimov A.A., Obidjonov Z.O., Aliyev A.A., Yuldasheva N.R. Remote measurement of the temperature generated on the surface of solar collectors	179
Usmanov Sh.Yu. Energy saving and ecologically perfect technologies	182
Madaminov M.R., Khosilov D.D., Yuldashev X.T. Improving the energy efficiency of reserve energy supply sources in the base stations of mobile networks	185
Rasakhodzhaev B.S., Quchqarov A.A., Boboeva M.O., Mashrapova I.R. Mamasadiqova Z.Yu. Thermal accumulators and their application in greenhouses	188
Khaydarov B.Z., Khakimov M.F., Dadajonova M.K. Infrared photography of objects based on a gas discharge cell	191
Kholiddinov I.Kh. Optimal power distribution of compensating devices between consumers of the radial power supply scheme	195
Eraliev Kh.A., Ibrohimov I.Z. Calculation of additional losses in Transformers with a asymmetrical load	199
Meliboyev I.A. Methods of neutralization and purification of waste gases	202
Alimova Z.Kh., Ismadiyrov A.A. Improving the performance properties of diesel oils used in Uzbekistan	205
Karabaeva M.I. Preparation of carbon adsorbents based on plant waste and study of their adsorption properties	208
Askarov Kh. Kh. Analytical study of the growth and development of Novruz mash variety (rhaseolis aireis piper)	211
Mirsalimova S.R., Jakbarov D.V. Study of synthesis and properties of benzimidazole derivatives	214
Sobirov A.O. Saline soils of fergana province and its use	216
Eminov Sh.O. Studying the properties of composite polymer coatings of working bodies of cotton processing machines	220
Arziyev S.S. The effectiveness of the use of holograms in teaching the discipline engineering computer graphics	222
Oltmisheva N.G., Tojiboyev U.U. Processes of democratic renewal and modernization in Uzbekistan	224
Makhmudov S.Y. Protection from ionizing radiation in daily activities	227
Abdullayeva M.A., Mirzaakbarov Q.Z. Creation of new interactive teaching methods for semiconductor relay protection devices in technical universities	229
Nishonova M.M. Problems and solutions of using intellectual systems in the educational process	233
Fozilov H.R. Some problems in the national statistics system in the digital economy and ways to solve them	235
Isomitdinov. G.K. Foreign state experience in assessing investment attractiveness in the digital economy	238
Abidova M.A. The use of new pedagogical technologies in the training of engineers-technologists	240
Khaidarov A.A. Innovative methods of teaching students of the "Food Technology" branch in organic chemistry	243
Mirzayeva G.S., Gafurov M. Measures to improve the working conditions of drivers engaged in the transportation of dangerous goods	246
Ergashov U.O. Goals and objectives of the organization of spiritual affairs	249
Akhunova M.Kh. Key issues of textile industry development	251
O'rinboeva M.S. Young people and norms of environmental ethics	253
Information to the authors !	259

Рис.2. Расчетная и измеренная экспериментальная кривые распределения плотности энергии лучистого потока в фокальной плоскости. 1 – расчетная кривая; 2 – экспериментальная кривая.

распределения плотности лучистого потока в фокальной плоскости параболоцилиндрической формы ЗКС.

Результаты расчета по (20) на примере предложенного метода расчета распределения плотности лучистого потока в оптической фокальной плоскости и экспериментальная кривая параболоцилиндрической формы ЗКС приведены на рис.2.

Таким образом, на базе выше указанных подходов выведено аналитическое выражение (20) для расчета распределения плотности лучистого потока от Солнца в фокальной оптической плоскости параболоцилиндрической ЗКС, что более точно описывают получаемые экспериментальные результаты.

Список литературы

- [1]. Баум В.А., Апариси Р. Р, Тепляков Д. И. Об объективной оценке точности оптических систем солнечных установок // Теплоэнергетика; под ред. Баума В. А.. – М.: Изд-во РАН, 1960. – С. 142-148.
- [2]. Захидов Р. А., Вайнер А. А., Умаров Г. Я. Теория и расчет гелиотехнических концентрирующих систем. – Ташкент: Фан, 1977. – 134 С.
- [3]. Zakhidov R.A., Klychev Sh.I., Maximum concentrating power of parabolocylindrical mirrors. Applied Solar Energy.1993.V.29.№ 4.pp, 56-58.
- [4]. Klychev Sh. I., Zakhidov R. A., Bakhranov S. A., Fasylov A. K., Dudko Yu. A., Solar radiation concentration in parabolocylindrical system with focusing wedge. Applied Solar Energy.2009.V.45.№ 2.pp, 99-101.
- [5]. Аванесов Э.С., Баум И.В. Аналитический расчет параболоцилиндрического концентратора с цилиндрическим приемником. Гелиотехника, 1984, №6, С.27-32.
- [6]. Аванесов Э.С., Баум И.В. Расчет энергетических характеристик параболоцилиндрического концентратора. Гелиотехника, 1986, №3, С.18-22.
- [7]. Мухитдинов М.М., Эргашев С.Ф., Солнечные параболоцилиндрические установки. Ташкент, Фан, 1995, 206 С.
- [8]. Жозе П. Распределение плотности энергии в фокальном изображении солнечной печи. в сб.
- [9]. Кудрин О.И. Солнечные высокотемпературные космические энергодвигательные установки. Москва “Машиностроение”, 1987г. - 248 С.
- [10]. Abdurakhmanov A. A., Kuchkarov A. A., Mamatkosimov M. A., Akhadov Zh. Z., The Optimization of the optical-geometric characteristics of mirror concentrating systems. Applied Solar Energy.2014.V.50.№ 4.pp, 244-251.

THE INFLUENCE OF MODERN MOBILE DEVICES ON THE PERFORMANCE OF STUDENTS

A.A. Abdumananov

*The Central Asian Medical University, Fergana polytechnic institute, Email: ahror79@inbox.ru
(Received on November 1 rd, 2022)*

The modern smartphones attract teachers and students with their opportunities to develop competencies with numerous applications, and at the same time, the obvious and yet insufficiently studied threats associated with smartphones cause concern and concern. Having a huge potential for use in the educational environment, the phone becomes a cause of conflict, a hindrance in lessons and a competitor to productive pastime. The paucity and inconsistency of data on the impact of the phone on academic achievement, psychological well-being, and interpersonal relationships require further research. The study

among junior students of the Institute considered the issues of productive and problematic use of mobile phones. The survey method was used to obtain information about the use of a mobile phone. One of the manifestations of the construct "problematic mobile phone use" is the presence of problems in various spheres of life, including problems related to school. As a result of the study, the positive and negative effects of mobile phones on educational activities were identified.

Keywords: mobile phone in education, mobile addiction, social networks, learning efficiency, learning activities.

Современные смартфоны привлекают преподавателей и студентов своими возможностями развивать компетенции с помощью многочисленных приложений, и в то же время очевидные и пока недостаточно изученные угрозы, связанные со смартфонами, вызывают беспокойство. Обладая огромным потенциалом для использования в образовательной среде, телефон становится причиной конфликтов, помехой на уроках и конкурентом продуктивному времяпрепровождению. Скудность и противоречивость данных о влиянии телефона на успеваемость, психологическое благополучие и межличностные отношения требуют дальнейших исследований. В исследовании среди студентов младших курсов института рассматривались вопросы продуктивного и проблемного использования мобильных телефонов. Метод опроса был использован для получения информации об использовании мобильного телефона. Одним из проявлений конструкта "проблемное использование мобильного телефона" является наличие проблем в различных сферах жизни, в том числе проблем, связанных со учебой. В результате исследования было выявлено положительное и отрицательное влияние мобильных телефонов на образовательную деятельность.

Ключевые слова: мобильный телефон в образовании, мобильная зависимость, социальные сети, эффективность обучения, учебная деятельность.

Zamonaviy smartfonlar o'qituvchilar va talabalarni malakalarini oshirish imkonini beruvchi ko'plab dasturlar bilan jalb qiladi va shu bilan birga smartfonlar bilan bog'liq hali to'la o'rganilmagan tahdidlar tashvishga solmoqda. Ta'lim muhitida foydalanish uchun katta imkoniyatlarga ega bo'lgan telefon nizolarni keltirib chiqaradi, darslarga xalaqit beradi va samarali vaqt o'tkazish uchun raqib bo'ladi. Telefonning akademik ko'rsatkichlarga, psixologik holatga va shaxslararo munosabatlarga ta'siri to'g'risidagi ma'lumotlarning kamligi va nomuvofiqligi qo'shimcha tadqiqotlarni talab qiladi. Institutning kichik kurs talabalari o'rtasida o'tkazilgan tadqiqotda mobil telefonlardan samarali va muammoli foydalanish masalalari ko'rib chiqildi. Mobil telefondan foydalanish to'g'risida ma'lumot olish uchun so'rovnoma usulidan foydalanilgan. "Uyali telefondan muammoli foydalanish" konstruksiyasining namoyon bo'lishidan biri bu hayotning turli sohalarida kundalik muammolar, shu jumladan ta'lim olish bilan bog'liq muammolarning mavjudligidir. Tadqiqot natijasida mobil telefonlarning ta'lim faoliyatiga ijobiy va salbiy ta'siri aniqlandi.

Kalit so'zlar: ta'limdagi mobil telefon, mobil qaramlik, ijtimoiy tarmoqlar, o'qitish samaradorligi, o'quv faoliyati.

The mobile phone is an essential part of modern life. Now it is difficult to imagine that this device was available to very few two decades ago, but at the moment it has become completely accessible to all categories of the population. The capabilities of modern phones go far beyond the simple transmission of information, it has become really mobile in terms of size and multiple functions, which naturally attract a lot of attention from young people. The current younger generation are great connoisseurs of all the functions that are presented in modern mobile devices. Since a mobile phone is not a stationary type of communication, it is used everywhere [10].

The relevance of this work is to determine the role of the mobile phone in the life of modern students and in the educational process. According to parents and teachers, a serious obstacle to the success of students in learning is an excessive fascination with the numerous possibilities of the phone. As students and active users of cellular communication services, we consider it very important for ourselves to determine the impact of excessive phone use in the learning process. This problem is very relevant for many, so we believe that this issue requires more in-depth study.

To study this issue, you need to solve the following tasks:

- Analyze information about the capabilities of modern mobile phones.
- Conduct a survey of teachers, students and their parents about the attitude of each of them to the use of mobile phones in the educational process;

- Conduct an experiment to identify the impact of mobile phones on academic performance among students.

The object of the study is the use of mobile phones by students.

The subject of the study is the impact of using mobile phones on students' academic performance.

Research methods: questionnaires and comparative analysis.

Mobile phones belong to the group of communicators, among which the most popular is the smartphone. A smartphone (from the English *smartphone* — literally translated from English means "smart phone") is a phone that has its own operating system, processor, and RAM. In addition to the price and popularity, the changes also affected the technical part: if in the first years of its existence the mobile phone was a simple tool for making calls, now it is almost a full-fledged computer that fits freely in your pocket. In recent years, there has been a boom: users' requests are growing, and manufacturers are outstripping each other every year, releasing more powerful processors, video chips, cameras, making the case thinner and the screen diagonal larger.

A smartphone differs from a regular phone in that it runs under the operating system. The most popular mobile operating systems at the moment are Android, iOS, and Windows Phone.

Also, with the development of performance, the capabilities of the smartphone also grow, they have more and more functions. Thanks to the operating system, smartphone owners have the opportunity to expand the functionality with additional applications. The widespread use of smartphones with a huge number of applications and services that expand the range of opportunities to meet various needs, the availability of a smartphone for every schoolchild and student lead to the question of the place and role of this mobile device in learning and the learning process. The multi-functionality of the smartphone provides its use as a means of operational access to information resources on the Internet, a device for communicating with other participants in the educational process, a display for displaying educational information presented in various forms (tests, media files). At the same time, a smartphone is a distracting object, a gadget that, given certain prerequisites, can become an object of forming addictive behavior (from the English *addiction* – an addiction, a vicious tendency in our case of smartphone addiction, mobile addiction) and other forms of mental disorders.

Research shows that having a mobile phone leads to a number of positive psychological effects, such as increased feelings of independence and autonomy. The phone provides an opportunity to establish and maintain positive relationships, to be connected with parents and friends. A number of negative consequences of excessive mobile phone use are also known: anxiety, loss of a sense of security, frequent mood changes, anxiety due to problems accessing services, feelings of isolation and abandonment if you do not receive the expected messages, sleep disorders, frequent awakenings to check for incoming messages or calls, physical symptoms (neck pain dry eyes, visual disturbances, etc., auditory and tactile hallucinations, delusions, *nomophobia* (fear of being left without a phone), etc.) [8].

There is evidence that even the very fact that a smartphone is turned on within easy reach (on a desk, in a bag) affects cognitive functions (memory and attention), reducing their productivity [9].

Recently, researchers have been attracted to the problem of the formation of dependence on a mobile phone (mobile addiction, smartphone addiction), the key feature of which is the inability to regulate the use of a mobile phone, which ultimately leads to negative consequences in everyday life. It should be noted that due to the relative novelty of the research issues, some of the issues around the key phenomenon of smartphone addiction remain debatable. The terminology used (mobile phone addiction, problematic or dysfunctional mobile phone use, etc.) continues to be discussed, the composition of the main components, and the reasons for the addiction (the phone itself or the content and activities offered by its apps). The very existence of addiction can also be called into question, since the symptoms associated with it are seen as a manifestation of other mental disorders.

Within the framework of the article, we focus on the concept of "problematic use", believing that it can also apply to situations related to the learning process. In this case, problems that arise due to phone use (for example, reduced academic performance, limited contact with peers, etc.) can be considered as manifestations of the phenomenon of problematic mobile phone use.

Understanding the reasons for the negative impact of the telephone on education can also contribute to the currently developed theories that are designed to explain the formation of telephone addiction. So, the theory of avoidance is based on the fact that mobile phones can be used to rid the painful self-consciousness of negative experiences and pressing problems. By focusing their attention on the "here and now", the user is protected from unpleasant thoughts and experiences related to existing problems, and thus reduces the discomfort and stress caused by stress.

A number of studies are devoted to the study of predictors of problematic phone use, such as neuroticism, extraversion, low self-esteem, and unfriendliness. J. Bellux [2] proposed an integrative theoretical model for the formation of phone addiction, which he named *Pathway Model of Problematic Mobile Phone Use*. The author believes that three paths can lead to the formation of problematic phone use: the path of excessive need for social support (an excessive reassurance pathway), the path of impulsivity and sociality, and the path of extraversion. Each of these pathways relates to a specific set of personality traits, the most popular mobile phone apps (features), the type of problematic phone use, and behavioral symptoms.

In adolescents and young men, a mobile phone can serve as a tool for reducing the level of loneliness. The constant desire to use the phone in this case is associated with the need to obtain guarantees of acceptance and with the fear of being rejected.

Data on the prevalence of mobile phone addiction, including during adolescence and adulthood, is very mixed. Indicators vary very widely –from 5 to 60 %, which is explained by differences in the definition of the evaluated construct itself, in the assessment methods used and the place of conducting.

Understanding the causes of problematic phone use in schools and universities, as well as developing preventive measures, requires taking into account the gender and age differences in the manifestations of phone addiction identified by research. It was found that the time spent on a mobile phone decreases with age. The highest rates were obtained for the age group under 20 years, where adolescents aged 14 and older predominate among addicts. The revealed dynamics is explained by the weakening of self-control, which is characteristic of adolescence. It was also found that girls, compared to boys, show a greater dependence on the phone, they are characterized by the predominant use of communication services and applications that provide opportunities to establish and maintain social connections, as well as serve to control negative emotions. Young people are distinguished by a tendency to risky use of the phone, great practicality and variety in using the phone's functions [6].

taking care of psychological well-being and providing conditions for effective study leads to the fact that the administration of educational organizations tries to limit the use of phones in the classroom and school, although many teachers recognize that the phone can be productively used in the classroom to search for information (as an alternative to less mobile tablets) and during classes outside taking a class (for example, for video and photo shooting of surveillance objects).

In France, the use of the phone at school is prohibited by law. In the UK, each school has the right to impose its own restrictions on the use of mobile phones, and bans can manifest themselves differently depending on the age of the student. For example, a 10-year-old student may be allowed to use the phone only once a week, an 11 – year-old may be allowed to use it three times, and so on. Such measures are aimed at creating a sense of responsibility and are designed to counteract the formation of dependence on a mobile phone. In one study conducted in the UK, it was found that banning the use of a phone at school among 16-year-olds increases test success by 6.4 % [1].

There are also no official bans or restrictions on using a mobile phone at school in our country. Each educational institution has the right to introduce its own restrictions, although most teachers, including the Minister of Education of the Russian Federation Vasilyeva, see it rather as a

hindrance to the learning process. At the same time, you can use your phone as a tool for solving individual educational tasks.

In higher education, there are no restrictions on using a smartphone. Survey data indicates that the majority of students use the phone for educational purposes. Moreover, specialized software and applications designed to solve educational problems are being developed, for example, providing access to electronic educational resources, libraries, and materials of distance courses. The list of ways to use a mobile phone compiled by experts for one study published in 2017 [7] included: translating texts, receiving and sending messages and e-mail about independent work, reading news, solving mathematical problems, viewing presentations and drawings in disciplines, recording lectures, taking notes during classes, practicing pronunciation, search for definitions, perform tests on disciplines online, record (video and audio) lectures and presentations, view recordings on academic subjects, post and upload training materials.

With the proliferation of smartphones, publications began to appear with research reports on the effects of using smartphones in educational activities. There are data [5] indicating an increase in academic achievement among students who used electronic devices, including smartphones. At the same time, a number of studies provide data indicating the existence of negative correlations of learning success with the use of the phone by students in higher educational institutions. Thus, negative correlations of academic performance with various types of learning-related activities carried out using the phone (correspondence about studying, copying class materials, downloading presentations, etc.) were obtained for a sample of university students in Malaysia [2]. Studies conducted in the United States [3] also led to conclusions about a negative relationship between the time spent using a smartphone and students' academic performance: the more time a student spends on a smartphone every day, the worse they perform on tests. Thus, intensive use of the phone, even for solving educational tasks, can negatively affect learning activities. Researchers attribute the explanation of the resulting dependence to the phenomenon of multitasking. The multi-functional nature of the phone and the presence of many applications inevitably create a multitasking situation that requires constant switching from one type of activity to another, including in the learning process. This leads to a deterioration in the assimilation of the material and a decrease in academic performance.

It can be stated that at the moment, the empirical material collected by researchers does not allow us to draw unambiguous conclusions about the psychological, educational and other consequences of using a smartphone in an educational environment. Our research was aimed at identifying the features of mobile phone use by high school students and students, as well as its impact on educational activities.

Participants of the study were 111 1-2-year students of the Ferghana Medical Institute of Public Health aged from 17 to 27 years. Respondents answered the questionnaire questions about mobile phone use and the Problematic Use of Mobile Phone (PUMP) scale, adapted by the authors of the article to study the severity of mobile phone addiction. Questions about the use of a mobile phone related to its possible negative and positive effects on the process and results of educational activities. The PUMP scale of problematic mobile phone use PUMP [4] is based on an extended model of the concept of telephone addiction, which includes, along with the symptoms common to all addictions, behavioral manifestations associated with excessive problematic phone use. The normative data obtained by the authors allow us to assign subjects to one of three assessment categories: norm, risk group, and pronounced problematic use (dependence). Data analysis was performed using the Excel statistical package. Gender and age of students were taken into account.

Research results. The survey revealed the presence of a smartphone in 100% of students. This ensures that most people have constant access to Internet services and applications and defines how to use the phone as a means of operational communication (messaging via social networks and instant messengers).

Figure 1-Diagram of the frequency of using various smartphone services.

Based on the data obtained (Figure1), we predicted that most of the time spent with the phone is spent communicating on social networks, but this indicator was not confirmed (41.4%). Quite often, the phone is used as a device for listening to music (56.8,8 %), for searching for non-academic information (74.8,8 %) and video viewing (60.4%) (at the same time, respondents claimed that they watch videos by subject and this proved the importance of creating video conventions in electronic educational resources), for making phone calls (83.8,8 %). With approximately the same frequency , the smartphone serves as a means for taking videos and photos (39.6 and 45.9%). Percentages correspond to the number of respondents who spend at least one hour on this type of activity every day.

As for the gender characteristics of phone use, young men are less likely to make calls ($p < 0.01$), but more likely to use the phone for games ($p < 0.01$) and watching videos ($p < 0.01$).

According to the PUMP questionnaire, 2.2% of students were found to have problematic mobile phone use, while 13.1 % were classified as at risk. It was found that problematic phone use positively correlates with the time spent on the Internet ($p < 0.01$), as well as certain types of activity using a mobile phone. The strongest correlation was found with the time spent in social networks ($R_{sp} = 0.45$, $p < 0.001$) and watching video and TV ($R_{sp} = 0.25$, $p < 0.01$). At a lower level ($p < 0.05$), links were obtained with the search for information not related to school, as well as with video and photography.

Analysis of the obtained correlations, taking into account gender, leads to the conclusion that the identified associations of problematic use are characteristic, first of all, for girls. Additionally, they have a significant and fairly strong correlation with listening to music. In young men, connections of problematic use do not reach a significant level. The impact of smartphones (both positive and negative) on students ' learning was assessed based on the analysis of responses to the questionnaire questions (Table 1).

Analysis of the responses showed that almost 20% of respondents agree that the smartphone takes time away from school, and another 34 % agreed with the "something in between" option, i.e. they recognized that the phone creates certain obstacles to preparing for classes at home. The

**ЭНЕРГЕТИКА, ЭЛЕКТРОТЕХНИКА, ЭЛЕКТРОННЫЕ ПРИБОРЫ И
ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ**

presence of a smartphone distracts from working in the audience, according to 42 % of respondents, 21 % agree and fully agree, and 21 % choose an ambivalent answer. The negative impact of the phone should also be attributed to its impact on cognitive processes—Reduced concentration of attention—is indicated (with varying degrees of agreement) by more than half of the respondents (56.9%).

Table 1.

The impact of a smartphone on your studies.

Statement	Totally disagree (%)	Disagree (%)	Something in between (%)	Agree (%)	Totally agree (%)	Correlation with the Pump
1 scale. Takes time away from studying in the process of preparing for classes at home	22.37	23.68	34.21	13.82	5.92	0.56
2. Distracts during classes in the classroom	26.80	31.37	20.92	15.03	5.88	0.40
3. Reduces the ability to concentrate	20.92	22.22	28.10	20.92	7.84	0.52
4. Allows you to get advice from competent persons	10.46	11.76	30.72	36.60	10.46	0.14
5. Allows you to read recommended textbooks, manuals, etc	9.87	7.89	15.13	44.08	23.03	0.03
6. Provides communication about studying with classmates and teachers	3,27	1,96	8,50	43,14	43,14	0,09
7. Helps relieve stress from studying and relax	7.19	13.07	29.41	30.07	20.26	0.39
8. Provides access to information sources	3,27	1,96	3,92	39,22	51,63	0,11

Students are more likely to agree with phrases where the phone is presented as a means of communicating about their studies, and the ability to read recommended literature and view video materials on subjects. However, students use their smartphone as a stress reliever less often ($p < 0.05$).

All three variants of the obvious negative impact of a smartphone on learning are related to each other and positively correlate with the PUMP scale score: the more dependence is shown, the greater the degree of agreement with statements in which the smartphone is associated with interference with learning. Smartphone addiction also positively correlates with the statement that the phone helps to relieve stress from studying, i.e. it acts as a means of mental self-regulation ($p < 0.01$).

The survey allows you to draw conclusions about productive smartphone use and recognize that having a phone creates new opportunities for students: 70 % agree that the phone allows you to use educational literature and resources, 47 % - to get advice, and 80 % - to communicate about their studies. It seems that the smartphone for students is really a tool that helps in their studies. The obtained correlations with the PUMP scale indicate that the reason for the negative impact may be the formed dependence on the smartphone.

The data obtained also allow us to assess the relationship between learning success and using a smartphone. As it turned out, academic performance is not related to how much time the

student spends with the phone. A weak negative correlation was obtained only with the time of listening to music ($p < 0.05$). The coefficients of rank correlation of academic performance with other types of activity using the phone turned out to be close to zero.

It was also found that academic performance is related to how much the phone distracts from studying at home or during classes in the classroom ($p < 0.05$). Teachers with high scores are less likely to consider the phone as a hindrance to studying in the walls of an educational institution or while preparing homework.

Summarizing the data obtained in the study, it can be argued that the impact of the phone on students' learning activities cannot be assessed unambiguously: there are positive effects and negative effects. The study shows that the problematic use of the phone by students, which hinders the achievement of educational tasks and reduces the productivity of learning, is a consequence of the formed dependence. The proposed model suggests that individual personality traits may serve as psychological prerequisites for the formation of addiction. It can be assumed that the age of the beginning of active mobile phone use is a predictor of the possible formation of problematic mobile phone use and its main components. The mobile phone is a unique way of coping with traditional problems of adolescence, performing a specific psychological protective function. Such problematic use of a mobile phone in adolescence is rather situational, and as the smartphone matures, it finds its true functional purpose, which does not exclude the initiation of appropriate joint preventive and preventive measures.

Referents

- [1]. Beland L.-P., Murphy R. Ill communication: technology, distraction and student performance // CEP Discussion Paper. 2015. № 1350.
- [2]. Billieux J. Problematic use of mobile phone: a literature review and a pathways model // Curr. Psychiatr. Rev. 2014. № 8 (4). P. 299-307.10
- [3]. Lepp A., Barkley J. E., Karpinski A. C. The relationship between cell phone use and academic performance in a sample of U. S. college students // SAGE Open. 2015. № 1–9.
- [4]. Merlo L. J., Stone A. M., Bibbey A. Measuring Problematic Mobile Phone Use: Development and Preliminary Psychometric Properties of the PUMP Scale // Journal of Addiction. 2013. Vol. 2013.
- [5]. Norries C., Hossain A., & Soloway E. Using smartphones as essential tools for learning: A call to place schools on the right side of the 21st century // Educational Technology. 2011. № 51 (3). P. 18-25.
- [6]. Roberts J. A., Petnji Yaya L. H., Manolis C. H. The invisible addiction: cell-phone activities and addiction among male and female college students // J. Behav. Addict. 2014. № 3. P. 254–265.
- [7]. Siew Foen [et al.] The Relationship Between Smartphone Use and Academic Performance: A Case of Students in a Malaysian Tertiary Institution // Malaysian Online Journal of Educational Technology. 2017. Vol. 5.
- [8]. Taneja C. The psychology of excessive cellular phone use // Delhi Psychiatry J. 2014. № 17. P. 448–451.
- [9]. Ward Adrian F., Duke Kristen, Gneezy Ayelet, Bos Maarten W. Brain Drain: The Mere Presence of One's Own Smartphone Reduces Available Cognitive Capacity // Journal of the Association for Consumer Research. 2017. № 2. P. 140-154.
- [10]. Абдуманонов А.А., Абсалямов Д. Р. Проблемы и задачи использования информационно-коммуникационных технологий в процессе самообразования студентов // НОВЫЕ ГОРИЗОНТЫ-2021 Сборник материалов VIII Белорусско-Китайского молодежного инновационного форума 11–12 ноября 2021 года, Минск -БНТУ -С. 77-79.

УДК 662.997; 669.054.8

A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW OF ENERGY STORAGE SYSTEMS: TECHNOLOGIES APPRAISAL AND GRID SCALE APPLICATIONS

A.A. Kuchkarov¹, D.U Khoshimov¹, I.N. Rakhmatshoev², A.Jumaboev¹

Fergana polytechnic institute, Uzbekistan

e-mail: diorbekxoshimov1757@mail.ru

(Received on November 1 rd, 2022)

From the past few years, the growing concerns on environmental effects due depletion of fossil fuels has resulted in transition towards RES to satisfy the global energy demand. Eco-friendliness, scalability and other extensive features of RES has attracted its deployment in commercial, industrial, and residential

ФарПИ ИЛМИЙ-ТЕХНИКА ЖУРНАЛИ
ТАХРИРИЯТИ:

Масъул мухаррир
Мусаххих
Мусаххих
Компьютерда саҳифаловчи

Н.Х. Юлдашев
А.Ш. Нигматуллина
Д.Х. Мамажонова
С.Э. Йўлдашева

Тахририят манзили:
150107. Фаргона шаҳри, Фаргона кўчаси, 86 уй.
Телефон: 241-13-54.
Факс: 241-12-06.
Бизнинг сайт: <http://www.ferpi.uz>
E-mail: jurnalferpi@mail.ru

Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президенти администрацияси ҳузуридаги
Ахборот ва оммавий коммуникациялар агентлиги томонидан
Оммавий ахборот воситаси сифатида давлат рўйхатидан ўтказилиб,
2020 йил 6 августда № 1081 рақамли гувоҳнома олинди.

Босишга рухсат этилди: 3.11.2022 й.
Бичими: А4. Гарнитура Times New Roman.
Босма табоги: 15,25. Адади 10 нусха. Буюртма № 3.
Баҳоси шартнома асосида.
«Alpha Print» босмаҳонасида чоп этилди.
Фаргона шаҳар, Фаргона кўчаси 86 -уй.
Лиц: №22-2891 21.11.2012 йил.